

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN *PARAPLECTANA* SPECIES

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For more information and credits for photographs see

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. S., HADDAD, C. R., FOORD, S. H., LOTZ, L. N. & WEBB, P. 2022. The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: part 3 (Ne-U). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 66 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326991

1. *Paraplectana thorntoni* (Blackwall, 1865)

Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022)

Pickard-Cambridge (1879)

Simon (1895)

Kolosváry (1931)

Colour variation Zimbabwe

2. *Paraplectana walleri* (Blackwall, 1865)

Simon (1895)

It resemble *Paraplectana hemisphaerica* (C.L. Koch, 1844) from Sierra Leone

Paraplectana sp. NEW

